

Spectrophotometric Determination of Gallium(III) with Chromotrope 2 R

S. C. DHUPAR, K. C. SRIVASTAVA & SAMIR K. BANERJI

Chemical Laboratories, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani

Received 27 December 1971; revised MSS received 30 May 1972

The reaction between gallium(III) and chromotrope 2R has been studied spectrophotometrically. The absorption maximum is at 580 nm against reagent blank at pH 3.4 ± 0.1 , Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 1.7–7.3 ppm of gallium. The chelate has a composition of 1 : 2 and the value of $\log K$ is 8.65 ± 0.05 (30°). The apparent molar extinction coefficient and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction are 17,312 and $0.004 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The effects due to 20 cations and 10 anions have been examined.

4,5-Dihydroxy-3-(phenylazo)-2,7-naphthalene disulphonic acid (disodium salt) [C.I. 16570; C.I. Acid Red 290; trivial name Chromotrope 2R abbr. CTR] reacts with many metal ions in acidic medium to form violet or reddish violet chelates and has been used in the photometric determination of various metals¹⁻⁶. This dye also reacts with gallium(III) to form a violet coloured chelate. The reaction has been applied to the spectrophotometric determination of gallium.

The purpose of these studies is to find the optimum conditions under which upto 7.3 ppm of gallium can be determined, to ascertain the effect of various diverse ions in the determination, and to determine the composition of the chelate formed. It has also been found that CTR ($\epsilon_{max} = 1.7312 \times 10^4$) is comparable in sensitivity with pyrocatechol violet⁷ ($\epsilon_{max} = 1.116 \times 10^4$), xylenol orange⁸ ($\epsilon_{max} = 1.6 \times 10^4$) and 1-pyrolidine-carbodithioate⁹ ($\epsilon_{max} = 2.58 \times 10^3$), which are used for the determination of gallium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of gallium chloride (Johnson Mathey & Co.) and CTR (BDH; purified by repeated precipitation with diethyl ether from its ethanolic solution) were prepared in double distilled water. The gallium content was estimated as gallium oxide (Ga_2O_3). The purity of the dye was checked by paper chromatography (R_F value 0.73). Solutions of various diverse ions were prepared from AnalaR grade reagents. For absorbance and pH measurements, Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer (Model 139) and Beckman pH meter (Model H2) were employed.

Measurements: All the solutions were kept in a constant temperature bath at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ for 1 hr previous to measurements. The pH of all the solutions was adjusted to $3.4^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ with NaOH or HCl (AnalaR) and ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 with NaClO_4 .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CTR shows maximum absorbance at 510 nm. Absorbance measurements with mixtures having various ratios of gallium to dye, show maximum absorbance at 580 nm, indicating that only one chelate is formed.

The effect of pH on the colour development was studied and it was noted that no complex is formed below pH 2.8 and above pH 4.8; maximum colour development is attained within the pH range 3.1 to 3.6. At pH 3.4 ± 0.1 and at 580 nm a fifty fold excess of reagent

TABLE 1

Diverse ion added	(ppm)	Relative % error	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Ce(III)	20	-87.6	0.46
Cu(II)	20	- 4.4	9.00
Zn(II)	20	- 9.7	4.10
Sn(II)	20	- 1.0	0.44
Be(II)	100	- 2.0	Large excess
Hg(II)	100	+ 5.5	36.40
Co(II)	20	- 3.4	11.80
Ni(II)	20	-18.3	2.20
Ba(II)	100	+ 2.0	Large excess
Cd(II)	100	-32.0	6.30
Pb(II)	100	+ 3.0	Large excess
Mg(II)	20	-28.2	1.40
Al(III)	5	+66.6	0.15
	80*	- 4.0	40.00
Tl(III)	40	-13.0	19.10
Fe(III)	20	+90.0	0.42
	80**	+ 5.7	28.07
Th(IV)	5	+92.4	0.11
	80***	+ 3.4	47.06
V(V)	20	-56.5	0.71
	60****	+ 5.6	21.40
Mo(VI)	20	-19.0	2.00
W(VI)	20	-33.1	1.20

* 70 ppm of F⁻ added. ** 60 ppm of F⁻ added. *** 20 ppm of F⁻ added. **** 1 cc of 1% ascorbic acid added.

concentration over that of metal ion ion concentration is necessary for maximum colour development.

Composition and formation constant : The mole ratio method, the slope-ratio method and continuous variations method were employed to establish the mole ratio of the chelate in solution, and it was concluded that gallium forms 1 : 2 chelate with CTR. The apparent formation constant was calculated from the mole-ratio curves and also by the measurements of molecular extinction coefficient, and the values of $\log K$ were 8.7 ± 0.1 and 8.6 ± 0.1 .

Adherence to Beer's Law : The colour system obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 1.7 to 7.3 ppm of gallium.

Molar Extinction Coefficient and Sensitivity : The apparent molecular extinction coefficient was found to be 17,312 and sensitivity of the reaction as expressed by Sandell's¹⁰ notation is 0.004 μg of gallium/ cm^2 .

The effect of cations : The effect of cations was examined at $\text{pH } 3.4 \pm 0.1$ and the tolerance limits were tentatively defined as the concentration of foreign ion which affects the absorbance of the system by less than 2%. The results are summarised in Table 1, from which it may be seen that Ce(III), Sn(II), Mg(II), Fe(III), Al(III), Th(IV), V(V), and W(VI) interfere at all concentrations. Al(III), Fe(III), and Th(IV) could be masked with appropriate amounts of fluoride ion. Vanadium(V) when reduced to V(IV) state with ascorbic acid prior to the addition of the ligand, could be tolerated to a large extent.

TABLE 2

Anions added	(ppm)	Relative % error	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Cl ⁻	100	- 3.2	Large excess
Br ⁻	100	- 0.0	Large excess
NO ₃ ⁻	100	- 2.1	Large excess
SO ₄ ⁻⁻	100	-45.0	4.4
SO ₃ ⁻⁻	100	-49.0	4.1
ClO ₄ ⁻	100	- 2.1	Large excess
CH ₃ COO ⁻	20	-41.9	0.96
C ₂ O ₄ ⁻⁻	20	-36.1	1.10
C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ ⁻⁻	20	-66.88	0.60
C ₆ H ₅ O ₇ ⁻	20	-61.8	0.65
BO ₃ ⁻⁻⁻	20	-31.1	1.30

The effect of anions : The results reported in table 2 show that acetate, oxalate, citrate, tartrate, and borate give negative errors when added in every small amounts. Bromide, chloride, nitrate, and chlorate do not interfere even at moderately high concentration.

Recommended Procedure : To a sample solution containing 1.7 to 7.3 ppm of gallium, 50-fold excess of CTR is added and pH adjusted to 3.4 ± 0.1 and finally the volume made 25 ml. The solution is allowed to stand for 30 mins and the absorbance of the solution is measured at 580 nm, against a reagent blank, treated in a similar manner. The concentration is read from a calibration curve obtained under identical condition.

The authors are thankful to Prof. C. R. Mitra, Director, B.I.T.S., Pilani, for providing laboratory facilities.

REFERENCES

1. Gr. Popa, D. Negoui and C. Vasilescue, *Acad. Rep. Populare Romine, Studii Cereetri chim.*, 1961, **9**, 629.
2. Gr. Popa and I. Parlescue, *Ser. Stiint. Nat.*, 1961, **10**, 203.
3. Gr. Popa and I. Parlescue, *Ser. Stiint. Nat.*, 1960, **9**, 103.
4. D. Negoui and M. Nasea, *Studia Univ. Babes-Bolyai Ser. Chem.*, 1963, **8** (1), 39.
5. V. L. Shah and S. P. Sangal, *Microchem. J.*, 1970, **15** (4), 548.
6. V. L. Shah and S. P. Sangal, *Chim. Anal. (Paris)*, 1971, **53**(1), 47.
7. M. K. Akhmedi, E. A. Bashikirov, E. L. Glushchenko and L. I. Zykova, *Ser. Khim. Nauk.*, 1965, **2**, 25.
8. M. Otomo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1965, **38**(2), 624.
9. W. Likussar, C. Sagan and F. B. David, *Mikrochim. Acta.*, 1970, **4**, 683.
10. E. B. Sandell, *Colorimetric determination of traces of metals*, 3rd edition, Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 83.